

Happiness, Media and Sustainability of Communities in Donkeaw, Mearim District, Chiang Mai, Thailand

Panida Jongsuksomsakul

Abstract—This study of the ‘happiness’ and ‘sustainability’ in the community of Donkeaw, Amphoe Mae Rim, Chiang Mai Province during the non-election period in Thailand, noted that their happiness levels are in the middle-average range. This was found using a mixed approach of qualitative and quantitative methods ($N = 386$, $\alpha = 0.05$). The study explores indicators for six aspects of well-being and happiness, including, good local governance, administrative support for the health system that maintains people’s mental and physical health, environment and weather, job security and a regular income aids them in managing a sustainable lifestyle. The impact of economic security and community relationships on social and cultural capital, and the way these aspects impact on the life style of the community, affects the sustainable well-being of people. Moreover, living with transparency and participatory communication led to diverse rewards in many areas.

Keywords—Communication, happiness, well-being, Donkeaw community, social and cultural capital.

I. INTRODUCTION

AFTER the military take-over of the civilian government in 2014 through a coup d'etat under the command of Royal Thai Armed Forces General Prayut Chan-o-cha, who consequently became the leader of the unelected government assuming the position as Prime Minister, the military government has wooed the Thai people through a sloganeering strategy aimed at bringing back their happiness. The first time he went on television, his promotion was said “Bring back happiness to all Thai”. Then, the population needs to ask him back, “What is the ‘happiness’” that the government hopes to bring ‘back’ to the Thai people? Compared to the Well-being policy and Economic Sufficiency and Sustainable Development Policy, the happiness of people is subjective in meaning and, with well-being and life satisfaction, should be measured individually. Happiness is the aim of people around the world.

According to the National Economic and Social Development Plan 12 (2017 – 2021) [1], Thailand needs to continue the sufficiency philosophy of King Bhumipol Adujadej (Rama IX). It is related human development, helping people to live better lives, towards the development of a ‘perfect’ and happy society. The way towards such a society, was the promotion of better public health and hygiene, as well as improved mental health. This plan advocates the development of improved international relations for the well-being of the people including, energy security, food security,

environment and well organised disaster management, and social security against crime and cyber-attacks. This project includes such aspects as health promotion, the promotion of tourism in the northern regions of Thailand, the promotion of the agricultural product industry, including the production of health food products, and places such as spas and massage parlours. Regulations applicable to the standardization of health foods, medicines, and health products such as vitamin supplements and Halal products, which are intended to keep people more healthy and reduce dependence on the medical profession, need to be passed and strengthened.

With regard to children, the provision of medical care and education is a priority. With regard to the elderly, provision needs to be made regarding appropriate medical care and community nursing care. These points are in keeping with the United Nations Development Plan and the Human Development Index.

In the World Happiness Index for 2017 [2], the top 10 nations for happiness were Norway, Denmark, Iceland, Switzerland, Finland, Netherlands, Canada, New Zealand, Australia and Sweden tied for the 9th position. Eighty percent of the variation in happiness across the world is related to internal (domestic) factors of countries. In richer countries, the internal differences cannot be attributed mainly to income inequality, but are influenced by differences in physical and mental health, and personal relationships. The biggest single cause of misery is mental illness. Income differences are more important in poorer countries, but even there mental illness is a major cause of misery.

Work is also a major factor affecting happiness within countries. Unemployment causes a sharp rise in unhappiness and misery. This even affects those who have work, as the working environment and the quality and nature of the work available, can be a source of misery. Part of the problem is that unscrupulous employers can use the unemployment situation to threaten and abuse employees.

In Thailand, many people speak about happiness [3]. From 2008 – 2012, the top five areas for happiness in Thailand were Nakornpanom Province, Pichit, Trang, Chaiyaphum, Krabi. The relationship between happiness and debt was considered between 2000 and 2003. People in the northern region have the lowest level of annual debt in Thailand. Monks and other religious leaders try to induce people to share resources as a source of happiness. These philosophies may have their roots in religious teaching; however, they open the giver to exploitation by the unscrupulous. In the news, there are examples of very wealthy people who commit suicide, suggesting that wealth, in itself, is not a source of happiness.

Panida Jongsuksomsakul is with the Communication Art Department, Faculty of Business, Economic and Communication, Naresuan University, Thailand (e-mail: pinitta@gmail.com).

There are reports where thieves may attack and even kill others in order to steal items that may be considered as valuable.

Industrial development significantly affects natural resources and the environment. People are facing global warming and energy shortages. In rural areas, communities are still close. By contrast, in major urban centres, people do not enjoy such close relations and tend to be more individualistic. The relationships are in a form of social and cultural capital. National development cannot be avoided. Communities therefore have to adapt to the changing situation. Change will ultimately affect livelihoods and relate to the happiness of people in the community. The principle of decentralization and the promoting of local administration have become key to the promoting of regional development in the form of provincial administration. Every sub-district has been allowed to set up an administration and is assessed by state agencies and educational institutions.

Donkaew community in Mea-rim District is one of these administrative organisations called 'Or-Bor-Tor'. It is an outlying district of Chiang Mai city, especially a residential one and the city. Local people there have been affected by increased urbanisation and the national development plan. From 2003 to 2017, the Donkaew Sub-district Administration Organization has received national awards from the Office of the Permanent Secretary, Office of the Prime Minister and various agencies such as the award of the best local administration organization and King Prajadhipok's Golden Prize in C.E 2012. Donkaew has also received a certificate for local government organisations with excellent transparency and public participation from King Prajadhipok's Institute Local Government Awards Good governance in line with good corporate governance, the 12th best local government award for networking with state, private and civil society [4]. These awards reflect transparency and cooperation against corruption by the community.

In addition, the changing state of communication technology does not reflect the aspect of the resident's happiness from within the community to the wider world. From outside the community, the administration is visible through the practice of participatory management. This participatory management is open to the media and allows the media to monitor their situation and any problems that may occur. It shows the sustainability of living in the Donkaew. This study aims to examine the following: What is the happiness of the people in the community? What does the community use to maintain social capital and cultural capital? How does social capital and cultural capital, lead to the cooperation of people in the area and affect the happiness of residents? And lastly, how does communication contribute to the sustainability of the community?

II. OBJECTIVES

To study devices of media and communication, social and cultural capital affected happiness and wellbeing of local people in Donkaew sub district, Mearim District, Chiang Mai Thailand.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

The appreciation of the nature of subjective well-being and its relation to happiness could enable the proponents and critics of subjective measures of happiness to develop a more precise measure of happiness in Thailand. This paper aims to integrate communication, social capital and cultural capital, which are indirectly involved into the measure of happiness and well-being.

Studies [5] investigated the links between social and economic status and well-being; the combination of economic and psychological approaches. To what extent, individual well-being is a (1) demographic characteristics (i.e., household income, age, education, employment, and length of residence); (2) perceptions of the city (e.g., local services and employment prospects) (3) attitudes toward political officials; (4) participation in community life; (5) SES, and (6) and reference income.

In this study the following seven dimensions were examined: 1) function of demographic characteristics (i.e., household income, age, education, employment and type of residents), 2) Job security (i.e. risk of their job, weather changeability, job stability) 3) Economic security (i.e., income, debt, sufficiency economic lifestyle.) 4) Family relationships and community engagement (i.e., conflict communication, solving problems communication, relationships in household and in community.) 5) Administrative management (i.e., participatory management, transparency administrative management.) 6) Social Environment and pollution in the community (i.e., drug problems, social problem, crime, environmental conditions, dust, noise, construction, floods, waste management.) and 7) Mental health and psychological affected. The first six dimensions were studied using in-depth interview with three local authority administrative boards. The seventh dimension was studied using the Thai Happiness Indicator (TMHI-15) in 2009 from the Department of Mental Health, Thailand.

The well-being measurement with a systems theory approach is used by the National Economic and Social Development and many other researchers in an effort to quantify "happiness," a subjective and individual issue, by first rating the basic living status of people. The human dimension should be added to fulfil the whole picture of this essential issue, and cultural aspect is definitely an important part of the human dimension. One unique thing about the people in Donkaew is their acceptance of new forms of media innovation. They allow the media to depict their cultural homogeneity. Local people here also possess other types of cultural capital such as funding from government and objects built for communication purposes such as a recycling depository project, the ancient reclining Buddha image, bicycle lanes, which also encourage tourists as cyclists, government offices, for example a military base, local kindergarten primary and secondary schools as well as websites and social networking online.

While many local communities launched mass media community radio and television projects, Donkaew uses only a public address system and also kept traditional media, such as

a northern fiddle or “Saw-U, Saw-Duang, who sing a song while playing instruments. The northern dancing style or “Fon Nguew” is also practiced. Most of the research on this area is concentrated in the disciplines of anthropology and sociology, and very little of it covers communication from socio-economic and microscopic approaches. Generally, social capital is related to a small-scale aggregation of social relations based on a network of trust and reciprocity and for the purpose of providing benefit to the members of the network reference [6].

Engaging in social activities and events helps to build interpersonal trust and these form the parts of social capital in society. Sharing simple things like a cup of coffee or tea with friends, participating in community activities, attending religious worship, taking part in volunteer activities, and engaging actively with neighbours and others in the community, all work to create social capital. Various social institutions within the community can help to encourage social interaction and the beliefs that enable a cycle of social connectedness and trust. The more socially active we are, the more we are able to trust others. For a community, frequent cooperation by its members is expected to lead to tighter social linkage and increased trust in one another. Support for this idea can be found in experimental research focusing on iterated prisoner’s dilemma games -- cooperation begets trust, which leads to further cooperation [7]. However, determining the flow of causation outside the laboratory is theoretically and methodologically complex.

Reference [8] suggested that social capital as an attribute that arises from the individual in a social context. Social capital can be acquired through purposeful actions and it can be transformed into conventional economic gain; that is, wealth. Whether this occurs or not depends on the nature of the social obligations, social connections, and other social situations available to the individual. Reference [9] went on to suggest that social capital is also a feature of social life networks, norms, and trust that facilitate cooperation and coordination to the mutual benefit of the individual and others in the community.

Therefore, for this research, the definition of social capital is social interaction based on a network of mutual trust in membership, reciprocity and on informal contract, and non-monetary exchange. The purpose of social capital is positive externality like trustworthiness, decreasing cost, no regulation, and audited expenses. Social capital can be measured in the form of objectives, output, or outcomes, as well as in system theory, as explained by [10], in the form of objects both in physical and abstract forms, attributes or assets and both internal successful and failure relationships, and environment. Normally, there are both closed and open systems that are wholeness and interdependence. A system is the correlation of relationships when one variable changes another; social and cultural capital also contains this characteristic. The greater the amount of social and cultural capital that is used, the greater the increasing return.

Mass modernization spreads culture across all kinds of media. Advertisements are a popular and direct form of

cultural transmission, although audiences might not be expected to always make cultural sense of its nuances; nonetheless, they bring about considerable consequences both in the art of products and guides to cultural consumption. The impacts are even stronger in selling techniques which enhance the role of symbol in the distribution process. Reference [11] explained that cultural economy means cultural economics and economics of arts that consist of all cultural products such as literature, arts, music, fashion and design, drama and journalism. Beside the reflection on the products, they also analysed the effects of culture on the consumption of those products. Furthermore, [12] shows that the mass media is able to form a link between cultural consumers and cultural production; therefore, it could be suggested that what is considered to be “symbolic economy” is based on abstract products and concepts including information financial tools, and “culture” (i.e. art, literature, fashion, music, tourism, etc.).

This economy is based on interrelated production of such cultural symbols and the spaces in which they are created and consumed including offices, houses, restaurants, museums, and even the streets; on this point, [13] poses the question “Is the economy becoming more cultural?” Most recent analyses of the relationship between culture and the economy assume that the boundaries between the two are collapsing. Moreover, it has been much more wildly asserted that there is more culture in the economy than the other way around. The term “culturalization” implies that culture has become more central in economic relations, a process usually implicitly considered good because no one is against more culture.

Several studies indicated that social capital is indirectly related to human beings. Social relationships are created mainly through communication. In 1993, scholars in Thailand set up a human and social development reference [14] index based on the eight categories of: fundamental basic environment, economy, health and public health, information and learning, education and human resources, culture and mind, public participation including security of life and freedoms, rights, and family and community.

Relational communication, a branch of the communication field, is greatly influenced by systems theory. Reference [15] referred to Bateson and other communication researchers to observe human behaviour, as done by the Palo Alto Group. From a systems point of view, behaviour is what matters. The structure of a relationship consists of these organized behavioural patterns. For example, our relationship with another person is determined by how the two of us act and what we say. Communication patterns are established through a sequence of actions or behaviours. When we communicate we take turns acting and reacting in sequence, and thus, our interaction is a flow of messages. Interaction is a basic unit of communication which forms through the human psyche and applied to communication. Interaction is a basic unit of communication which forms through the human psyche and applied to communication. An interaction is a set of two contiguous messages between two people. Interactions are combined into larger units called double interactions, and the latter are combined yet again into triple interactions. The

structure of an entire interaction system is composed of larger and larger sets of interactions. Interactions combine to become a culture. Unless, an interaction rejects communication, it is a common feature of life. As a result, the media has interacted with people consistently over time, and are therefore able to influence audiences.

The theory that people purposefully use media is founded on the functionalist perspectives of mass media communication, known as the use and gratification theory (U&G). It was first developed out of research on the effectiveness of the radio as a communication medium in the 1940s. It focuses on an explanation for audience members' motivations and associated behaviours. Former, scholars of psychology coined the term 'gratifications' to depict the specific dimensions of usage and satisfaction of radio audiences. It is still used to analyse the gratification of social media usage.

U&G research has the basic assumption that audiences are actively involved in media use and interact strongly with communication media. Following this concept; it was adjusted to analyse data obtained from the Internet such as seeking information via Facebook and similar uses for the Internet. Studies found the same usage purposes of receivers as other scholars found in similar studies done on radio and television. The similarity of human acquisitions in using communication media is social interaction, the development and maintenance of relationships with colleagues and other friends, and finding other more distant friendships. Even they have differing formats, but these applications are now integrated into one gadget and can fit to human communication habits. For example, [16] found that certain kinds of television programs have been shown to be related to various human needs, including information acquisition, escape, emotional release, companionship, reality exploration, and value reinforcement.

In conclusion, these perspectives were adopted to serve the purpose of the present analysis, especially the methods of measurement and concepts that demonstrate how communication, social capital, and cultural capital affect the well-being of people, and the researcher's understanding of the use of systems theory and gratification.

A. Hypotheses and Research Questions

Based on the literature review, the hypotheses and research questions of this research include the following:

- H1.** The relationship of socio-economic status to the well-being of local people in the Donkeaw community.
- RQ1.** How does the well-being of local people in the Donkeaw community relate to socio-economic status?
- H2.** The relationship of communication type to the well-being of local people in the Donkeaw Community.
- RQ2.** What kind of communication type is related to the well-being of local people in the Donkeaw Community?

B. Methodology

Sample: A domestic office in Donkeaw collected data in 30 September 2014 [17] and found that there were 14, 639 people

and 2,486 households there. Administrative areas cover 34,953 m². Land use means that local people live, broadly, in four areas; three of the four areas include: the government centre where administrative functions take place, areas allocated for military use and an area that is set aside as a nature reserve. Using purposive and stratified sampling methods, data were selected from 10 villages are Bo-pu village, Donkeaw Village, Sala and Huaytuengtoa Village, Pangae Village, Pranon Village, Paruak Village, Sanmuang Village, Chayang Village, Sobsanongphan Village and Prachaonungkon Village with a sample size of 400 people using Taro Yamane's formula with a 5% margin of error ($p=0.05$). Forty questionnaires were distributed per village, and the rest went to the downtown area. Of the 400 questionnaires distributed, 398 were returned to the researcher and used for regression and factor analysis.

1. Variables

The socio-economic status variables reported were sex, age, marital status, education, literacy, job, income, and health insurance. Responses were recorded from closed-ended multiple-choice questions.

The well-being index was composed of six dimensions, namely, 1) health dimension: mental and physical health including health insurance; 2) job security dimension: regular income, pride in what you do, job security, freedom to work, seasonal income, unstable costs; 3) economic security dimension: sufficient income per month per household to maintain a reasonable lifestyle, savings status, risk of unemployment, economic crisis, expenditure control; 4) family relationships: personal respect, family communication, shared activities as a family, type of family, independence, social relevance, norm and family risk taking, drugs and alcohol abuse in family; 5) administrative management dimension: public places (e.g., parks, library, playground, bicycle lanes), public communication (i.e., public address, leaflets, pamphlets, website, social network), good governance, public participation in local governance such as planning, monitoring, budget transparency, election voting and access to public welfare 6) social environment and pollution dimension: living environment, problems in local area (i.e., crime, drugs, noise, alcohol, waste). The response scale ranged from 1 (not at all important/ not at all agree) to 10 (very important/strongly agree).

Types of communication were separated into personal communication, interpersonal communication, group communication, and mass communication in people's daily lives. For this, the question was "How often do you use any form of communication?" Responses were ranked on a four-point scale (where a value of 4 means often or more than 10 hours a day, 3 means sometimes or 5-10 hours a day, 2 means rarely or 1- 4 hours a day and 1 means never or zero hours a day).

The reliability and validity of the questions were determined from professors and 30 people who were familiar with the background of the samples. Internal consistency of the data was determined by using Cronbach's alpha test. The

resultant coefficient of ($\alpha = 0.736$ or $r = 0.74$) was higher than the standardized alpha (0.6). Therefore, the questionnaire was deemed to be appropriate for this research measurement. The wording and number scale were also adjusted from 1- 5 to 1-10 to improve inter-personal consistency, and intra-item and inter-item consistency.

In the questionnaire, a series of questions refer to well-being, cultural traditions and community activities using a scale from 1 to 10. With the use of the MAX-MIN-CON principle, the main objective of the research was to gauge happiness (8.21 - 10.00 means very happy; 6.41 - 8.20 means average happiness; 4.61 - 6.40 means almost happy; 2.81 - 4.60 means less happy; and 1.00 - 2.80 means really not happy).

After descriptive analysis, relations among the variables were analysed by factor and multivariate analysis, and the results are reported below.

2. Findings

a. Happiness and Well-Being Average and SES Status

This study found that 386 responses have an average happiness score of 5.9, which means that they are moderate in their well-being.

Descriptive statistics showed that more responses were received from females than males, the age of respondents was between 16-88 years old, with an average age of 51 years, and the number of married respondents was moderate (61.9%). Those who are single through divorce or death are referred to as separated. The responses showed that 97.4% of the people in the samples were literate, 36% had only primary school level education, 21.5% had finished high school and 17.1% had graduated with bachelor degrees. Over 50% of samples are household leaders, living in Donkeaw permanently, and the remainder are temporary residents for government employment and migrant work.

On average, 21.8% had an income of more than 20,000 baht, 19.4% had incomes of 10,000-14,999 baht per month, and 16.1% had an income of 5,000-7,999 baht per month, and 14.5% had less than 5,000 baht, and an equal number had an income of 8,000-9,999 baht a month. With regard to occupation, the responses showed that 26.4% were labourers both in private organizations and general service, 22.5% were business owners, 19.2% are government officials or state enterprise officers, 19% were unemployed, 9.1% were industrial workers and the rest were farmers. Some of them had no debt (39.1%) and 32.1% had debt, while 111 people did not fill in the form.

Almost all of them had access to government health insurance and were on the free cure program; the remainder were receiving government welfare and unemployment benefits. They also had insurance policies that they paid by themselves. As they are volunteer health workers in the community, they are eligible for free health care in their local clinic. This result reflects the good medical welfare available for Thai people and an indication of advances in the health care program, at least in terms of equity.

b. Media Use Variables

All media variables were measured dichotomously, with respondents indicating that they did or did not watch a given program. Indices of media use were constructed using descriptive and the Pearson Chi-Square analysis, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I
MEDIA EXPOSURE IN DAILY LIFE

Daily life media aspect	Mean	S.D.
1. Personal Communication in the village: Neighbours, head of village, monks, and family members.	7.14	2.51
2. Local mass media: Advertising on caravans and moving vehicles.	4.88	2.62
3. Local mass media: News speaker towers and wire broadcasting in villages.	7.68	5.51
4. Mass media: Thairath newspaper, Daily news newspaper and Komchudluek newspaper.	5.40	3.03
5. Mass media: Matichon newspaper, Prachachart newspaper and Krungthep business newspaper.	3.76	2.76
6. Local mass media: Local newspaper.	4.12	2.96
7. Mass media: Listens to political programmes broadcast on the radio.	3.89	2.87
8. Mass media: Listen to entertaining broadcasts on satellite radio.	4.72	3.04
9. Mass media: Listen to music on Chiang Mai radio broadcasting.	4.51	3.10
10. Mass media: Television i.e., channels 3, 5, 7, and 9 and Thai PBS.	7.94	2.41
11. Local mass media: Channel PRD (NBT).	5.35	3.01
12. Group communication: Local government officers i.e., local village volunteer, participation in meetings with local staff.	6.92	2.85
13. Leaflets, newsletters.	5.36	2.92
14. Internet and social network i.e., Facebook, LINE, Twitter.	4.94	3.55

Local community members perceived information from the four top most sources: The first is Mass media including television i.e., channel 3, channel 5, channel 7, and channel 9 and Thai PBS with an average of 7.94, second is Local mass media including news speaker towers and wire broadcasting in the village with an average of 7.68, third is Personal Communication in the village such as neighbours, head of the village, monks, and family members with an average of 7.14, and the fourth is Group communication: Local government officers i.e., local village volunteer, participation in meeting with local staff, with an average of 6.92.

They received a medium score for their use of local mass media (local newspapers), small printed media such as leaflets, newsletters) and the local mass media Channel PRD (NBT), Thairath newspaper, Daily news newspaper and Komchudluek newspaper, Internet and social networks i.e., Facebook, LINE, Twitter, and listening to entertaining broadcasts on satellite radio and advertising on moving vehicles.

Lastly, less perception usage media are local newspapers, listening to music on Chiang Mai radio broadcasting, Matichon newspapers, Prachachart newspapers and Krungthep business newspaper, and listening to political programme broadcasts on the radio.

Considered by mean and SD, the results for mass media are similar for broadcasts, and newspapers, as well as for community radio and local media exposure. This means that

mass media impacts on all audiences. Interpersonal communication refers to contact with neighbours, family, and government officers who contributing to and discussing ideas. The Internet was sometimes used to seek information.

Over half of the total media exposure was reading newspapers every morning (35.5%), watching television, listening to the radio and reading newspapers online after work and on days off (32.6%). Some of them listen to radio all day long (17.6%) and watch television on and off over the day (16.6%); and read newspapers while having dinner or lunch (16.3%). Nonetheless, 15% of the respondents were online 24 hours a day, e.g. teenagers who use mobile phones and social networks. They check their mobile phones on-and-off throughout the night.

Over half of the subjects (54.8%) are between 31-90 years of age and spent more than 10 hours a day online using Facebook, Twitter, LINE, etc., and only 6.2% of the subjects' are between 16-45 years of age and are online for more than 10 hours a day.

With regards to other media, those aged between 46-60 years spent 1-4 hours a day listening to the radio (50.6%), reading newspapers (33.1%), listening to community media (32.4%), and talking to monks, friends and family (31%). About 29.5% of the people talked to others via mobile phone, and 28% received traditional media. In terms of the five types of communication: mass media, interpersonal communication and group communication, community media, traditional media and new media, respondents were exposed to mass media for more than 10 hours a day and sometimes (5-10 hours a day) received interpersonal media and traditional media, while only 1-4 hours a day is spent with new media such as Internet surfing and social networking.

As for content from the various media outlets (Fig. 1), most of the sample received political (36.8%) and occupational (33.7%) information, entertainment (12.7%), art and culture (9.7%), agriculture (4.8%) and sport (2.3%).

Fig. 1 Content exposure from various sources

All channel uses were related to type of information perceived ($p < 0.05$), e.g. news, entertainment, factual information, etc. Surprisingly, the research found that the Internet was not a significant channel for receiving political and entertainment news. People in the sample, on average were 18-49 years old, and they were not regular Internet users. Moreover, political topics were usually discussed privately. Television also provided political and entertainment news.

The findings for watching movies, watching television and listening to the radio were reported in the health and mind dimension ($\bar{x} = 5.26$, S.D = 2.27). This confirms that communication exposure supports people's mindfulness and relaxation by watching movies, watching television programs, and listening to health and morality programs. Nonetheless, Korean drama series and primetime Thai drama shows were the favourite programs; both satisfied people and increased their happiness to some extent.

These uses of media and the gratifications accrued may contribute to the production of social capital both in positive and negative ways. These informational uses of the media may provide people with issues or problems that they feel deserve their attention; for example, personal identity uses may supply people with ways of understanding themselves and their social world. Furthermore, integration and social interaction uses may offer people a model for social behaviour that they can emulate in their life by allowing them to connect with others and be happy. In contrast, entertainment uses may also be detrimental to social capital and cultural capital because a major function of such media use is to amuse and distract.

3. Happiness Indicators

The overall means of happiness indicators on the six aspects of well-being included mental and physical health dimension: mental and physical health including health insurance (mental and physical health aspect) is on average ($\bar{x} = 6.0$); job security including regular income, pride in what you do, job security, freedom to work, seasonal income, unstable costs (job security aspect) is on average ($\bar{x} = 5.7$); economic dimension including sufficient income per month per household to maintain a reasonable lifestyle, savings status, risk of unemployment, economic crisis, expenditure control (economic security aspect) is on average ($\bar{x} = 4.9$); family relationship dimension including personal respect, family communication, shared activities as a family, type of family, independence, social relevance, norm and family risk taking, drug and alcohol abuse in the family (family relationships aspect) is in the high level of happiness ($\bar{x} = 7.3$); and administrative dimension including public places (e.g., parks, library, playground, bicycle lanes), public communication (i.e., public address, leaflets, pamphlets, website, social network), good governance, public participation in local governance such as planning, monitoring, budget transparency, election voting and access to public welfare (administrative management aspect) is at a high level ($\bar{x} = 6.9$) and social environment dimension including living environment, problems in local area i.e., crime, drugs, noise, alcohol, waste, (social environment aspect) is in lowest level ($\bar{x} = 3.8$).

Mean happiness measured from 115 devices was 5.9 (out of 10) noted that their happiness levels are in the middle-average range. Further, previous research has demonstrated that measure of life satisfaction – the cognitive component of well-being – have test–retest reliabilities of around 0.6 [18]. The loading for the single-item measure of well-being was fixed a priori at 0.7 to be consistent with this research. Details on happiness of each aspect are as follows:

First Dimension: Health - they indicated happy, fresh and lively, calm and peaceful, feeling powerful, depressed with life and nothing better, sense of hopelessness, nervous, worry about the political situation in Thailand, relaxation by travel, meditate and practice religious activities, exercise for health,

exercise to relax and relieve stress, able to live and let live without stress, you are going to see the doctor and go to hospital, watching movies and listen to music for relaxation, when you are ill do you go to Donkeaw Community clinic and get enough rest and sleep well.

The indices of the health aspect were created by factor analysis using *Varimax* rotation to separate the individual responses of 15 distinct items. The analysis, which accounted for $\sigma^2 = 60.485$ of variance in the nine items, yielded a three-factor solution that was highly interpretable. Each item loaded on only three factors; all items had strong factor loading (see Table II).

TABLE II
 FACTOR ANALYSIS OF MENTAL AND PHYSICAL HEALTH ASPECT AND RELIABILITY OF RESULTANT INDICES

Mental and Physical Health Aspect	Factor loading				Reliability
	1	2	3	4	
1. Feel Happy	0.793				25.403
2. Lively/Fresh	0.764				
3. Calm and Peaceful	0.748				
4. Feeling powerful	0.705				
5. Depressed with life and nothing better		0.842			17.675
6. Sense of hopelessness		0.833			
7. Nervous		0.773			
8. Worry about the political situation in Thailand		0.632			
9. Relaxation by travel		0.528			8.435
10. Meditate and practice religious activities			0.843		
11. Exercise for health			0.775		
12. Exercise to relax and relieve stress			0.628		
13. Able to live and let live without stress			0.559		7.587
14. To see the doctor and go to hospital				0.771	
15. Watching movies and listen to music for relaxation				0.591	
16. When you are ill you go to Donkeaw Community Clinic				0.562	
17. Get enough rest and sleep well	0.509			0.522	

The health aspect index was developed for this study by adding all responses to items concerning viewpoints on “*Well-being and Happiness of Mind*”, “*Suffering*”, “*Relax and Seeking for Happiness*”, and “*Good Health and Mind*”. The four-item index achieved $\alpha = 25.403, 17.675, 8.435, \text{ and } 7.587$, respectively.

a. Dimension 2: Job Security Aspect

Second Dimension: Job security - respondents indicated their Present job security insurance on average = 6.71, Regular income = 6.67, Occupation at risk from natural disaster and climate change =3.23, Seasons effected to income =3.58, Occupation at risk from market price =4.37, Pride in job =7.43, Sufficient income=6.82, and Itinerant workers or freelance = 6.80.

The indices of the job security aspect were created by factor analysis using *Varimax* rotation to separate individual responses of the eight distinct items. The analysis, which accounted $\sigma^2 = 66.967$ of variance in the eight items, yielded a two-factor solution that was highly interpretable. Each item was loaded on only three factors; all items had also strong factor loading (see Table III).

Indices of the job security aspect were created by factor analysis using *Varimax* rotation to separate individual responses of the 8 distinct items. The analysis, which accounted $\sigma^2 = 66.967$ of variance in the eight items, yielded a two-factor solution that was highly interpretable. Each item was loaded on only three factors; all items had also strong factor loading (see Table III).

TABLE III
 FACTOR ANALYSIS OF JOB SECURITY ASPECT AND RELIABILITY OF RESULTANT INDICES

Job Security Aspect	Factor loading		Reliability
	1	2	
1. Present job security insurance	0.880		48.168
2. Regular income	0.866		
3. Climate change and weather effect to agriculture.	0.844		18.799
4. Remuneration depends on weather.	0.818		
5. Market price affected to remuneration.	0.682		
6. Pride in job		0.830	
7. Sufficient income		0.741	0.714
8. Itinerant or freelance		0.714	

The job security aspect index was developed by adding all

responses to items concerning viewpoints on the external factors regular income and job security, and risk of job and income. The two-item index achieved $\alpha = 48.168$ and 18.79 , respectively.

b. Dimension 3: Economic Security Aspect

Third Dimension: Economic security aspect - they indicated at Present have financial security (income is sufficient to allow saving) on average = 5.26, Have health problems which incur more expense = 3.33, Manage regular account – household expenses = 3.59, Manageable debt = 5.16, Occupation depends on national economic security = 4.10, Income satisfaction = 6.11, and Economic sufficiency lifestyle = 6.41.

The indices of the economic security aspect were created by factor analysis using *Varimax* rotation to separate individual responses for the seven distinct items. The analysis, which accounted for $\sigma^2 = 53.76$ of variance in the seven items, yielded a two-factor solution. Each item was loaded on only one factor; all items had also a strong factor loading (see Table IV).

TABLE IV
 FACTOR ANALYSIS FOR THE ECONOMIC SECURITY ASPECT AND RELIABILITY OF THE RESULTANT INDICES

Economic Security Aspect	Factor loading		Reliability
	1	2	
1. Have financial security (income is sufficient to allow saving)	0.835		36.32
2. Have health problems which incur more expense	0.745		
3. Manage regular account – household expenses	0.685		
4. Manageable debt		0.684	17.44
5. Occupation depends on national economic security		0.633	
6. Income satisfaction		0.565	
7. Economic sufficiency lifestyle		0.541	

The economic security aspect index was developed by adding all responses to items concerning viewpoints on “Economic Sufficiency” and “Occupation Depends on National Economic Security and Manageable Debt”. The two-factor index achieved $\alpha = 36.32$ and 17.44 , respectively.

c. Dimension 4: Community and Family Relationships Aspect

Fourth Dimension: Community and family relationships aspect- they indicated at Present have financial security (income is sufficient to allow saving) on average = 5.26, Have health problems which incur more expense = 3.33, Manage regular account – household expenses = 3.59, Manageable debt = 5.16, Occupation depends on national economic security = 4.10, Income satisfaction = 6.11, and Economic sufficiency lifestyle = 6.41.

Indices of the community and family relationships aspect were created by factor analysis using *Varimax* rotation to separate individual responses of the nine distinct items. The analysis, which accounted for $\sigma^2 = 72.662$ of variance in the eight items, yielded a two-factor solution that was highly interpretable. Each item was loaded on only two factors; all

items also had strong factor loading (see Table V).

TABLE V
 FACTOR ANALYSIS OF COMMUNITY AND FAMILY RELATIONSHIPS ASPECT AND RELIABILITY OF RESULTANT INDICES

Community and Family Relationships Aspect	Factor loading		Reliability
	1	2	
1. Family has honour and sincerity	0.947		57.481
2. Family has a close relationship	0.944		
3. Family communicates at all times	0.929		
4. Problems are discussed within the family all times	0.922		
5. Family is supportive and helps each other	0.914		
6. Family does activities together	0.709		
7. Family talks with neighbours regularly		0.804	15.181
8. Family joins religious activities regularly		0.579	
9. Family member(s) smoke and drink alcohol		0.497	

The Community and Family Relationships Aspect index was developed by adding all responses to items concerning viewpoints on “communication and close and love relationship in family” and “solving problem with communication in family”. The two-item index achieved $\alpha = 57.481$ and 15.181 , respectively.

d. Dimension 5: Administrative and Local Government Organization Management Aspect

Indices of the administrative and local government organization management aspect were created by factor analysis using *Varimax* rotation to separate individual responses of the 21 distinct items. The analysis, which accounted for $\sigma^2 = 64.273$ of variance in the five items, yielded a five-factor solution that was highly interpretable. Each item was loaded on only five factors; all items had also strong factor loading (see Table VI).

The administrative and local government organization management aspect index was developed by adding all responses to items concerning viewpoints on “participatory communication and management in community”, “good governance”, and “administrative transparency” and “community participatory management”. The two-item index achieved $\alpha = 20.969$, 17.009 , 11.52 , 8.172 and 6.063 , respectively.

e. Dimension 6: Environment and Climate in Community Area Aspect

Indices of the environment and climate in community area aspect were created by factor analysis using *Varimax* rotation to separate individual responses of the 12 distinct items. The analysis, which accounted for $\sigma^2 = 62.869$ of variance in the three items, yielded a three-factor solution that was highly interpretable. Each item was loaded on only five factors; all items had also strong factor loading (see Table VII).

The environment and climate in the community index was developed by adding all responses to items concerning viewpoints on “condition of environment problems in the community”, “condition of social problems in the community” and “climate and environment in the community”. The three-item index achieved $\alpha = 30.166$, 18.039 and 14.664 ,

respectively.

TABLE VI
FACTOR ADMINISTRATIVE AND LOCAL GOVERNMENT ORGANIZATION MANAGEMENT ASPECT AND RELIABILITY OF RESULTANT INDICES

Administrative and Local Government Organization Management Aspect	Factor loading					Reliability		
	1	2	3	4	5			
1. Local government provides public parks, fitness and exercise equipment which are meeting places in the community.	0.765					20.969		
2. Small media in the community such as radio, bulletin boards, mobile speakers, and leaflets are the main information channels.	0.752							
3. Community leaders have respect and engage in participatory and transparent management.	0.699							
4. Members of the community help each other.	0.699							
5. Members of the community receive information from others, including officials, about local activities.	0.695							
6. Local Organization Management or Or-Bor-Tor looks after problems in the community.	0.576							
7. Local government inspects the community for safety.	0.570							
8. Local organization officials work honestly and sincerely with people.		0.806					17.009	
9. Local government provides regular budgets for community needs.		0.683						
10. Officials in local organisations are usually local people with local family connections.		0.641						
11. Justice and civil protection is the responsibility of local organisations.		0.624						
12. Local community organisations treat people according to the relevant laws and accepted rules.		0.587						
13. Local staff occupies most positions in local organisations.		0.498						
14. Local religious leaders make people feel proud of their land and community.			0.784			11.52		
15. Local people have equal access to health care.			0.691					
16. Successful local governance makes the people of Donkeaw proud of their community.			0.597					
17. The various parts of the local government and the local community all cooperate and work together.			.579					
18. Members of the community help each other and participate in the planning and development of projects.				.831				8.172
19. The community is informed of the contents of local budgets.				.737				
20. Local people are able to participate in and state their views in local meetings.					.848		6.063	
21. People are able to elect local officials.					-.646			

TABLE VII
FACTOR ANALYSIS OF ENVIRONMENT AND CLIMATE IN COMMUNITY ASPECT AND RELIABILITY OF RESULTANT INDICES

The Environment, Climate and Community Aspects	Factor loading			Reliability
	1	2	3	
1. Smoke, carbon or soot in the area because of garage and industrial activities.	0.827			30.166
2. Dust, smoke and carbon from cars in your area.	0.812			
3. Polluted water released in the community.	0.797			
4. Noise pollution in your community.	0.781			
5. Dumped waste causing bad smells in the environment.	0.766			
6. Juvenile drug addiction, police and legal responses.		0.873		18.039
7. Drugs and drug addiction in the community.		0.801		
8. Juvenile offenders receive guidance and still have a chance.		0.574	0.554	
9. There is a crime problem in your community.		0.536		
10. Road construction and heavy traffic cause inconvenience for community transport.			0.686	14.664
11. Hot and humid weather makes people feel uncomfortable.			0.659	
12. Local organizations are able to solve community problems.			0.619	

f. Dimension 7: Media Perceived Aspect

The Aspect of Indices of the Media in Daily Life was created by factor analysis using *Varimax* rotation to separate individual responses of the 14 distinct items. The analysis, which accounted for $\sigma^2 = 63$ of variance in the three items, yielded a three-factor solution that was highly interpretable. Each item was loaded on only four factors; all items had also strong factor loading (see Table VIII).

The Aspect of the Media in Daily Life index was developed by adding all responses to items concerning viewpoints on “radio broadcasting”, “newspapers”, “community media” and

“television broadcasting, the “Internet and social networks”. The four-item index achieved $\alpha = 33.227, 13.004, 8.749$ and 8.010 , respectively. Then, using regression analysis with Enter Method Technique to find the correlation (R) and prediction Coefficient of determinism (R^2) and measure the coefficient of determination (R^2 change) F ratio (F) and proportion of coefficient of determinism (F change) from various measures can predict the well-being of the Donkeaw community people (Y), as shown in Table IX.

TABLE VIII
FACTOR ANALYSIS FOR THE ASPECT OF MEDIA IN DAILY LIFE AND RELIABILITY OF RESULTANT INDICES

	The Aspect of Media in Daily life	Factor loading				Reliability
		1	2	3	4	
1.	Mass media: listen to entertainment programming broadcast on satellite radio.	0.852				33.227
2.	Mass media: listen to music broadcast on Chiang Mai radio.	0.820				
3.	Mass media: listens to political programming broadcast on the local radio.	0.792				
4.	Mass media: Matichon newspaper, Prachachart newspaper and Krungthep business newspaper.		0.750			13.004
5.	Mass media: Thairath newspaper, Daily news newspaper and Komchudluek newspaper.		0.711			
6.	Local newspapers.		0.678			
7.	Advertising on vehicles.		0.624			
8.	Group communication: local government officers i.e., local village volunteers, participate in meetings with local officials.			0.810		8.749
9.	Leaflets, Newsletters.			0.733		
10.	Local mass media: news speaker towers and wire broadcasting in the village community.			0.555		
11.	Personal Communication in the village: neighbours, head of village, monks, and family members.			0.535		
12.	Local mass media: Channel PRD (NBT).			0.494		
13.	Mass media: Television i.e., channels 3, 5, 7, 9 and Thai PBS.				0.704	8.010
14.	Internet and social network i.e., Facebook, LINE, Twitter.				0.687	

TABLE IX
REGRESSION COEFFICIENT OF WELL-BEING FACTORS

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	0.987 ^a	0.974	0.972

$R^2 = 0.974$ means 97.4% of coefficient determinism or factors of well-being indicates a strong positive and significant correlation ($p < 0.05$). Model no. 1 explains that at least one variable from 26 variables relate to happiness ($R = 98.7\%$). Durbin-Watson is 1.883. The score is 1.5-2.5, meaning that it is independent.

This determinism is a dependent variable or community happiness acquires 97.4% only 2.6% have other variables that affect happiness (Y). The happiness sampling (386 people) increases 5.9 when the *well-being and happiness of the mind* item increases 0.77, the suffering *item* decreases 0.62. The watch television and social media usage item decreases to 0.03, the reading newspaper item decreased to 0.06, manageable debt item increased 0.05, while the regular income item increases 0.034, and the cultural pride item of culture and tourism increased to 0.5. Details on the determinism equation are each explained below.

- 1) Physical health and mental health figure increased to 0.77. This suggests that the local population have an increased feeling of well-being, are feeling fresh, at peace, calm and relaxed, powerful, release and are able to sleep well could increase.
- 2) Suffering decreased to 0.62, suggesting that people in the community feel less depressed and discouraged. They have less to worry about and feel more positive about the future, worry about the current political situation.
- 3) Media exposure such as newspapers, television and social networks online aspects decreases to 0.03, meaning that the local population made less use of the Media. They, for example, receive news and other information from channels such as Thai PBS, Channel 9, Channel 7, Channel 5, Channel 3 and digital information online (i.e., Facebook, Line, Twitter) including newspapers (i.e., Matichon, Prachachart, Krungthep Business, Thairath,

Daily news, Kom Chud Leuk) would be happier.

- 4) Manageable Debt Aspect increases to 0.05 meaning that people in the community are mainly involved in agriculture which is subject to seasonal variation. If the Thai economy is stable and they have access to health and related benefits, they feel more positive. If, on the other hand, the economy is less stable and they are ill and have limited access to health and other benefits, they feel less positive and may find it difficult to pay their way, and therefore may incur debts.
- 5) Income and job security aspect increases to 0.034 meaning that regular income, pride in one's job, financial security (income is sufficient to allow saving) and the management of regular accounts – household expenses are increased.

4. Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

All the variables and relationship summaries (positive and negative) of well-being and socioeconomics are shown in Tables I-VII. A positive relationship between socioeconomics and communication and well-being was predicted; the link was expected to be stronger from the economic point of view. Some community members are in debt. Nonetheless, they were satisfied with their income and life. Debt is not related to the amount of savings that they have in the bank (p -value=0.06) and Hypothesis 1 is rejected that socioeconomics is related to happiness ($F=6.88$, sig $0.00 < 0.05$). Inter-correlations with the average monthly income of more than 20,000 baht were examined to ensure that collinearity would achieve a value of 0.89 ($p < 0.005$). The mean of 88 variables can be used to calculate the happiness score (5.9). This suggests that the community is moderately happy and that direct financial concerns are less important.

As these people are labourers, business owners and government officials or state enterprise officers, they need to be able to pay their way, and this can mean that they need to go into debt. In the case of labourers and government officials, they had to take out study loans from the government in order to pay for their education. These loans need to be repaid. So

long as the repayment is not too heavy, these people are able to manage; however, the loans may take years to repay.

Some of these people are land owners and they are able to secure loans against the value of their land (mortgage). The mortgage can be repaid using money accrued as rent or income from the land. They do not have to repay their loans from their other income. If these people lose their jobs for any reason, they are able to return to their land and to agricultural production. This is in keeping with the sufficiency philosophy of the late King Bhumibol Aduyadej Rama, IX.

According to the philosophy of sufficiency, the leader of Donkeaw district and the government, cooperate in teaching the community new agricultural techniques and also new means of waste management such as the “waste bank”. In this system, the waste is taken to a collection point where it is separated. Biological waste is turned into fertilizers, metals, plastics and papers are recycled (see Fig. 2). The community attends public meetings where they can express their own views of what is needed and the use of available funds. This enables the community as a whole to work together. The attendance of these meetings; are examples of participatory communication (See Figs. 3 and 4). As this is a primary form of communication in this community, it is their primary form of media usage, these meeting allow for all decisions to be transparent; therefore, they have good governance. They also have less need for mass media as their systems are so transparent. The mass media serves to keep the community informed of events beyond their community.

The correlation between the medial uses index and well-being is examined in the absence of controls. The analysis revealed a correlation of traditional media, interpersonal media, mass media, and new media. Meanwhile, the test of Hypothesis 2 is rejected that communication usage is related to happiness (using Pearson correlation $r= 0.422$, sig $0.00 < 0.05$). It is indicated that the relationship of communication type, which is interpersonal communication, has a relationship to the well-being of local people in the Donkeaw Community. The mass media have visited the area and reported on the success of community endeavours such as the ‘waste bank’ project and their award for transparency, public participation in community affairs and good governance. This is indicative of the openness and community spirit of the people in the area.

Fig. 2 The waste process

Fig. 3 Public meeting

Fig. 4 Budget meeting

5. Discussion and Conclusion

People in the community read the newspapers or watch television to be informed of outside events or for political information or for entertainment purposes. Some of them appear to ‘multitask’ by using several forms of mass media at once. In the community, people talk in a group following the media agenda and gossip about drama actors/actresses or programmes shown on TV. At the end of a working day, the people of Donkeaw visit the monks to discuss matters of concern and to make offerings. Some of the people are village volunteer workers or traditional wise ones. They like to play Lanna, a form of traditional northern music, make handicrafts and perform Lanna dances. These aspects are cultural capital, social capital, communication capital that affects the happiness in the community, even though their happiness score is not high; rather it is in the middle levels.

The findings of this study suggest that socioeconomic factors, communication, social capital and cultural capital all significantly relate to the levels of happiness experienced by the people of Donkeaw. The patterns reveal parallel positive and negative associations between various socioeconomic factors, especially factors such as income and job security, economic security, the environment and physical and mental health. These factors are all interrelated and cannot be easily separated. With the use of traditional media, and traditional stories, the community is able to hold itself together without the use of modern media.

Happiness relates to government policies, laws, the granting of a budget to every community and village, so long as there is sufficient funding to meet any perceived needs. People in the community who are in good mental and physical health, living

in sufficiency economic, cultural and communication capital, feel as though they are able to cope with their lives and are unlikely to oppose government, as happened in the past when people rose up in opposition to government as they felt that their futures were being compromised. Distributing budgets fairly and administering them transparently through local government could potentially do this. Interestingly, it was also found that local leaders who are native to the area are more successful at achieving this than other leaders because they know how to improve their area first-hand.

Besides economic matters, cultural factors and the importance of communication and the media may be seen as a “symbolic economy” [12], [13]. The results of research into the mass media, has led to the assumption that modern media, including television, radio, the Internet and social networks have exposed the way of life of consumers to outsiders. In Thailand, digital television created forms of television programme such as game shows, singing contests, reality game shows, amusement programmes, etc., which are related to Thai people.

The result in the media perceived that many shows have political motives and any information gained from them to be political. Other kinds of television programmes are aimed at various human needs. These needs include, among other things, the acquisition of information, entertainment, companionship, the exploration of personal reality, and the underlining of personal and social values.

Surveys of digital media have led to the ranking of popular programmes as indicated in the rating below for shows during 1 – 30 April 2017 [19]. These surveys were carried out predominately in small urban areas, and cannot therefore be considered reliable for the country as a whole. The survey only considers entertainment programmes in the top 10 popular programmes. A criticism would be that these surveys do not consider a sufficiently broad spectrum of the population of the country to be considered entirely reliable.

The results of this study are in contrast to a survey by the National Broadcasting Telecommunication Committee [20]. Even though television still popular among Thai audiences, under the influence of powerful global media, local media is still important as it is easy to run and it is accessible to wide ranging local audiences. Meanwhile, the government usually subsidizes local radio and television projects in areas related to knowledge [21]. Conventional Public address system in local area (please see pictures below) of a village in the local area of Donkeaw, along with websites associated with the area are good ways to connect with local people. Health promotion volunteers, for example, use social media and services such as LINE, and Facebook to post internal news and other public information.

Mass media in Thailand consists of radio, television, but also the experiences and unity of a community that comes from participation in public meetings and online is integrated into the social network via Facebook, Twitter, the YouTube channels and similar forms of social media. Local organisations tracking the same line are able to interact with local people online and present public information. According

to reference [21], while communication creates networks of relationships among local people who form the structure of the community, networks connect groups with one another, help to form beliefs, values and modify behaviour. Groups that come to share more are said to experience convergence and groups that share less, experience divergence. Social network application is able to support and increase communication with people who are inclined to communicate less. The amount of variation within the group increases and the structure of the system break apart and entropy prevails. This suggests that social media may be able to help those who find it difficult to maintain contact with others, as it provides a means to maintain contact over distance.

nielsen
Average TV RATING: Primetime(18:20-22:30)(1-30 April 60)

15+ Nationwide			Bangkok			Urban			Rural		
Rank	Channel	Rating	Rank	Channel	Rating	Rank	Channel	Rating	Rank	Channel	Rating
1	7	5.655	1	7	4.574	1	7	4.460	1	7	6.462
2	3	3.623	2	3	4.216	2	3	4.318	2	3	3.123
3	3	3.281	3	3	4.209	3	3	3.799	3	3	2.470
4	one si	1.536	4	one si	1.407	4	one si	1.344	4	one si	1.413
5	29	1.406	5	one si	1.343	5	29	1.204	5	7	1.413
6	7	1.274	6	7	1.042	6	7	0.892	6	29	1.412
7	7	0.871	7	3	0.624	7	7	0.883	7	Boomerang	0.728
8	True TV 32	0.643	8	True TV 32	0.606	8	Boomerang	0.693	8	7	0.718
9	3	0.586	9	3	0.496	9	True TV 32	0.586	9	3	0.604
10	NOW 25	0.533	10	NOW 25	0.484	10	3	0.526	10	NOW 25	0.576
11	Boomerang	0.504	11	3	0.481	11	NOW 25	0.491	11	True TV 32	0.573
12	NOW 25	0.471	12	Boomerang	0.480	12	NOW 25	0.444	12	M Channel	0.453
13	true4U	0.433	13	true4U	0.456	13	7	0.400	13	NOW 25	0.415

Fig. 5 Average TV Rating: Primetime during 1-30 April 2017 [19]

Fig. 6 Public Address System in Donkeaw Local Area

With an increase in communication within a group more is shared, structure develops, with the result that there is convergence. This principle also applies between groups. As contact between groups increase, they become more alike. If they lose contact, differences develop and become clearer. People often experience this personally when they lose touch with old friends and form new friendships; this process forms the base for cultural differences.

Culture is nothing more than common ways of thinking and behaving which develop because of relatively isolated group communication. Differences form between cultures because there is less contact between them, than there is between members of individual cultures. If everybody communicated with others outside their culture as much as they do in the

group, cultures would soon disappear. Nonetheless, it can be said that from an economic viewpoint, culture and social relations are capital. If both are incorporated in a tourist activity, it would increase income for everyone. This may be good for smaller more isolated communities, as it would provide more economic advantages for local people, and therefore they would be less inclined to move away to search for work. The following illustration depicts this conclusion:

Fig. 7 System shows how communication affects people's well-being

This study found that communication brings many social political and economic factors together where they are entwined and cannot be easily separated. Communication is a variable of social capital and networking, especially face-to-face communication. Modern communication systems such as computer networks have to be treated with considerable caution, as the sources of available information may be difficult to verify. Most of the people in Donkeaw find that the younger generation leave and go to major urban centres such as Bangkok or Chiang Mai. They do not have much time to visit and rely on the telephone to communicate with family and friends in Donkeaw. This may be the reason why local residents visit the temples and talk to the monks. The local administration organisations such as hospitals, military camps, universities, juvenile probation centres, local clinics, etc. always create activities for older people, for example, massage with herbs and facilities for bedridden patients. Local governments help to promote better health among local people, by providing sports equipment, bicycle lanes, and other facilities in parks and public places.

To sum up, happiness or well-being includes economic conditions and conceptions which are at the centre of the capitalist ideology. It is unlikely to be rejected, but rather, it may be sustained. Serving people to be happy in their lives, governments have to assume all indices as mentioned above. Happiness can be mentioned using the seven aspects of health, knowledge, economics, job security, environment, good governance, and social relationships. None of these aspects can be separated from culture and communication.

It is suggested that the factors arising from this study may be divided, in a broad sense, into two categories: policy suggestions and practical suggestions.

a. Policy Suggestion

- 1.1 Policy of downsizing power of national government. Government authority needs, wherever possible, to be transferred from the central authority in Bangkok to the local provincial and district authorities. This transfer of authority needs to be carefully carried out so as to maintain the principle of law and measurement with standardisation.
- 1.2 Happiness policies in Thailand should be maintained according to the sustainable and sufficiency philosophy of King Bhumibol Adulyadej (King Rama IX). According to the Social and Economic Development Strategy for the 20 Year Plan (Activated during 2017-2037), almost of the activities and budgets follow the Digital 4.0 policy. However, the Sustainable and Sufficiency Philosophy of King Rama IX is the first priority and was announced by UNESCO in remembrance of the Great King. These policies include programmes to consider the happiness of the Thai people. It concerns, inter alia, the use of digital media. It does not of itself, directly affect people in terms of their mental well-being or their community relations.

b. Practical Suggestions

- 2.1 The promotion of good living conditions with participatory communication and conflict resolution to local areas, both give and take ideas to understand local contexts. The inclusion of local needs and contexts can be taken as part of the national policy documents.
- 2.2 Communication is the mechanism of everything for everyone, especially the mass media among digital media, as everyone can have access to and therefore use media devices. Such digital media however needs to be used with caution, as they can reach the stage of overuse which can have a negative impact on the well-being of the user.

IV. LIMITATIONS

Due to limited time, the results from this research were unfortunately only produced for the Donkeaw area. The degree of reliability and efficiency could be increased if samples from other areas in Thailand were included.

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